

STRESSES DUE TO ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONING OF CROSS-PLY GRAPHITE/EPOXY LAMINATES

by David A. DOUGLASS

*Sr. Structures Engineer, Bell Helicopter Textron
Fort Worth, Texas*

and Yechiel WEITSMAN

*Professor
Mechanics and Materials Center
Texas A&M University
College Station, Texas*

This paper concerns the internal residual stresses due to the environmental conditioning of cross-ply graphite/epoxy laminates, where moisture is induced into the material by exposure to high relative humidity at elevated temperatures.

The stress fields resulting from conditioning at two temperature levels are evaluated for a balanced, symmetric cross-ply graphite/epoxy laminate by means of both elastic and viscoelastic analyses. The formulation considers temperature-dependent moisture diffusion and time, temperature and moisture dependent stress relaxation. The computations are based upon recent data and employ realistic values of material parameters.

The analysis shows that the viscoelastic stresses are much smaller than those predicted by elastic analysis, and that conditioning at 150°F results in residual stresses which are smaller than those reached during conditioning at 180°F.

INTRODUCTION

Increasing concern with the effects of temperature and moisture on the performance of composites demands the development of accelerated conditioning techniques. These conditioning schemes attempt to simulate extreme exposures to moisture and temperature which may be encountered in service life.

Since moisture diffuses extremely slow the conditioning process is accelerated by employing elevated temperatures which accelerate the moisture sorption and shorten the duration of the experiment.

It was observed that certain conditioning schemes induce damage in the composite. In order to develop time saving, yet non-damaging, laboratory experiments it is necessary to predict the stresses which arise due to moisture and temperature in composite laminates.

In this paper the moisture and temperature effects are incorporated into a viscoelastic constitutive relation, which is based upon creep data at various levels of temperatures and moisture contents. It is noted that both environmental factors act as swelling agents, which introduce stresses in the presence of geometric constraints. On the other hand, both moisture and temperature enhance the relaxation of stresses, thus compensating for their initial effects. While this "competition" is accounted for in the viscoelastic representation it cannot be considered within the context of an elastic response. Consequently, test articles which were conditioned in different manners will contain disparate residual stresses and perform differently under loads.

In this paper we consider a symmetric, balanced, cross-ply laminate. Results are presented for two conditioning schemes and comparison is provided with an elastic analysis. Additional results and further details are given in Ref. [1].

PRELIMINARY CONSIDERATIONS

For clarity we present individually the major factors present in moisture conditioning.

Moisture Diffusion

The diffusion into thin composite laminates is found to follow Fick's second law [2], [3], which in one dimension reads

$$\frac{\partial m}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 m}{\partial z^2} \quad (1)$$

The solution to (1), under steady ambient conditions is given in two alternate forms [4]

$$m(z, t) = m_a - (m_a - m_0) \left\{ 1 - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{n+1} \left[\operatorname{erfc} \left(\frac{2n-1-z/h}{2\sqrt{t^*}} \right) + \operatorname{erfc} \left(\frac{2n-1+z/h}{2\sqrt{t^*}} \right) \right] \right\} \quad (2)$$

and

$$m(z, t) = m_a - (m_a - m_0) \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2}{\mu_n} (-1)^{n+1} \cos \left(\frac{\mu_n z}{h} \right) \exp(-\mu_n^2 t^*) \quad (3)$$

where the dimensionless time t^* is given by $t^* = \frac{Dt}{h^2}$, and in (3)

$$\mu_n = \frac{(2n-1)\pi}{2}$$

It can be shown that for $t^* < 0.29$ (2) converges rapidly while for $t^* > 0.29$ form (3) is more advantageous. In (1), (2) and (3) m is moisture, m_a is the constant ambient moisture, m_0 is a uniform initial moisture, z is the spatial

coordinate across the thickness, t is time and D the moisture diffusivity.

It has been found [5] that the saturation level m_a depends on the relative humidity RH . In graphite/epoxy systems a linear relationship $m_a = E(RH)$ is employed. In addition, the diffusion coefficient D is temperature dependent [6]. This dependence is given by $D(T) = A_1 \exp(-B_1/T)$.

Swelling Due to Moisture

The transverse swelling of most graphite/epoxy systems due to moisture absorption is sketched in Fig. 1 [7, 8]. The phenomenon is characterized by a moisture expansion coefficient β_T .

Fig. 1. Transverse Swelling Vs. Moisture Content

The transverse strain due to moisture swelling is expressed as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_T &= \beta_T (m - m_1) \quad \text{for } m \geq m_1 \\ \epsilon_T &= 0 \quad \quad \quad \text{for } m \leq m_1 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

In (4) m_1 is a threshold value below which moisture is not accompanied by any transverse swelling.

Measurements also indicate that the longitudinal swelling coefficient is negligibly small and we shall take $\beta_L = 0$.

Temperature Diffusion and Thermal Expansion

Data on temperature diffusion indicate that, for typical laminates, this process preceeds much faster than all other time-dependent processes. Therefore we shall disregard temperature diffusion and consider spatially uniform, thermally equilibrated states.

In unidirectional laminae the thermal strains are completely characterized by the longitudinal and transverse coefficients of thermal expansion α_L and α_T .

Geometry and Notation

We shall consider symmetric, $0^\circ/90^\circ$ lay-ups and let the principal material axes coincide with the x - y coordinates. The x axis is chosen parallel to the fibers in the 0° plies. Whenever necessary we shall employ subscripts L and T to denote longitudinal and transverse directions. See Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Laminate Geometry and Notation.

Viscoelastic Behavior

The viscoelastic response of graphite/epoxy laminates in the transverse direction is of paramount significance during environmental conditioning. The time-dependent transverse compliance S_T can be expressed by a "power law" equation [9]

$$S_T = D_0(T,H) + D_1 \left(\frac{t}{a(T,H)} \right)^q \quad (5)$$

where D_0 is the initial compliance, t is time, $a(T,H)$ is the shift factor function which depends on humidity and temperature, and D_1 and q are material constants. The dependence of D_0 on T and H can be expressed by [9] $D_0(T,H) = aTH + bT + cH + d$.

However, in order to simplify computations we shall approximate $D_0(T,H)$ by its average value over the range of T and H in each conditioning scheme. This approximation entails errors of about 5%.

The data on the shift-factor function $a(T,H)$ can be expressed by

$$a(T,H) = a_1(T)a_2(H) \quad \text{where} \\ \log a_1(T) = a_3 + a_4(1/T) + a_5(1/T)^2 \quad \text{and} \quad (6) \\ a_2(H) = a_6 m^{b_1}$$

The compliances S_L and S_{12} do not exhibit time, temperature and moisture dependence.

Elastic Compliances and Moduli

We shall take all elastic compliances and moduli as the initial viscoelastic values. Moduli are inverses of compliances, as follows

$$C_L = D_0/\Delta, \quad C_T = S_L/\Delta, \quad C_{12} = -S_{12}/\Delta, \quad \text{where } \Delta = S_L D_0 - S_{12}^2. \quad (7)$$

Combined Stress - Strain Relations

Elastic

The combined elastic stress-strain relations for the plies considered herein, and for a state of plane stress, are

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma_x^0 &= C_L \epsilon_x + C_{12} \epsilon_y - (C_L \alpha_L + C_{12} \alpha_T) \Delta T - C_{12} \beta_T (m - m_1) - C_L \beta_L m \\
 \sigma_x^{90} &= C_T \epsilon_x + C_{12} \epsilon_y - (C_T \alpha_T + C_{12} \alpha_L) \Delta T - C_T \beta_T (m - m_1) - C_{12} \beta_L m \\
 \sigma_y^0 &= C_{12} \epsilon_x + C_T \epsilon_y - (C_T \alpha_T + C_{12} \alpha_L) \Delta T - C_T \beta_T (m - m_1) - C_{12} \beta_L m \\
 \sigma_y^{90} &= C_{12} \epsilon_x + C_L \epsilon_y - (C_L \alpha_L + C_{12} \alpha_T) \Delta T - C_{12} \beta_T (m - m_1) - C_L \beta_L m
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

where superscripts 0 and 90 denote ply orientations. It should be borne in mind that since $m = m(z, t)$, all stresses depend on z and t . However for the sake of notational brevity this dependence is suppressed.

Viscoelastic

In analogy with (8) the viscoelastic stress-strain relations for combined effects [10], expressed in terms of compliances, are

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{L1} \sigma_x^0 + S_{12} \sigma_y^0 &= R_1^0 \\
 S_{12} \sigma_x^0 + D_0 \sigma_y^0 + D_1 \int_0^t (\xi - \xi')^q \frac{d\sigma_y^0}{d\tau} d\tau &= R_2^0 \\
 D_0 \sigma_x^{90} + D_1 \int_0^t (\xi - \xi')^q \frac{d\sigma_x^{90}}{d\tau} d\tau + S_{12} \sigma_y^{90} &= R_1^{90}
 \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

$$S_{12} \sigma_x^{90} + S_{L1} \sigma_y^{90} = R_2^{90} \quad \text{where, in (9)}$$

$$\xi = \xi(z, t) = \int_0^t \frac{ds}{a(T(s), m(z, s))}, \quad \xi' = \xi'(z, \tau) = \int_0^\tau \frac{ds}{a(T(s), m(z, s))}$$

and

$$R_1^0 = \epsilon_x - \beta_L m - \alpha_L \Delta T, \quad R_1^{90} = \epsilon_x - \beta_T (m - m_1) - \alpha_T \Delta T,$$

$$R_2^0 = \epsilon_y - \beta_T (m - m_1) - \alpha_T \Delta T, \quad R_2^{90} = \epsilon_y - \beta_L m - \alpha_L \Delta T.$$

ELASTIC STRESS ANALYSIS

Consider a symmetric laminate composed of N_0 0° plies and N_{90} 90° plies. The laminate undergoes a total temperature change ΔT , which consists of cooling from cure to room temperature and then heating to the desired level of conditioning temperature at which moisture conditioning is enhanced. The laminate also absorbs moisture during storage prior to conditioning and due to conditioning at increased humidity. All this time the laminate is free of external loads.

The elastic stresses are obtained by superposing the solution for a geometrically constrained case, in which the moisture sorption and temperature variation are considered without any deformation, and the solution for strain fields $\epsilon_x(t)$ and $\epsilon_y(t)$ which are uniform throughout the thickness. The superposition is effected in such a manner that the net resultant forces F_x and F_y , in the x and y directions respectively, vanish. The requirements $\Sigma F_x = 0$, $\Sigma F_y = 0$, represent the absence of externally applied loads, but are insufficient to account for detailed edge effects, and provide the equations to determine the strains $\epsilon_x(t)$ and $\epsilon_y(t)$. Since the moisture profile at each time is known from the solution to the diffusion equation, denote the total contribution to swelling due to moisture in, say, the

i^{th} ply by

$$e_T(M_1^\phi) = \beta_T \int_{\text{Thickness of } i^{\text{th}} \text{ ply}} (m - m_1) dz \quad (10)$$

In (10), the superscript ϕ , which may be 0° or 90° , indicates the orientation of the i^{th} ply. Consequently, the cumulative transverse swelling due to moisture for all 0° plies is

$$e_T(M^0(t)) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_0} e_T(M_i^0)$$

and similarly for the 90° plies

$$e_T(M^{90}(t)) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{90}} e_T(M_i^{90})$$

The total longitudinal swelling can be obtained in an analogous manner. However, since we take $\beta_L = 0$, these analogous terms will vanish in our case.

Denote h^0 and h^{90} as the total thickness of all of the 0° and 90° plies respectively, then employment of (8) together with the equilibrium requirements $\Sigma F_x = 0$, $\Sigma F_y = 0$ yield

$$\begin{aligned} (h^0 C_L + h^{90} C_T) \epsilon_x + (h^0 + h^{90}) C_{12} \epsilon_y &= R_1 \\ (h^0 + h^{90}) C_{12} \epsilon_x + (h^0 C_T + h^{90} C_L) \epsilon_y &= R_2 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} R_1 &= C_L e_L(M^0) + C_{12} e_T(M^0) + C_T e_T(M^{90}) + C_{12} e_L(M^{90}) \\ &\quad + h^0 (C_L \alpha_L + C_{12} \alpha_T) \Delta T + h^{90} (C_T \alpha_T + C_{12} \alpha_L) \Delta T \\ R_2 &= C_{12} e_L(M^0) + C_T e_T(M^0) + C_{12} e_T(M^{90}) + C_L e_L(M^{90}) \\ &\quad + h^0 (C_T \alpha_T + C_{12} \alpha_L) \Delta T + h^{90} (C_L \alpha_L + C_{12} \alpha_T) \Delta T \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

The simultaneous solution of (11) yields the values of the time-dependent strains ϵ_x and ϵ_y . The stress profile due to temperature and moisture conditioning is obtained by substituting the strains from (11) into (8).

The time-dependent elastic stresses are thus determined for all times until moisture saturation is reached for each particular conditioning scheme. At this stage, the temperature is lowered down to room temperature, causing sudden increments in all stresses. These increments are obtained by solving a simplified version of (11), (12) and (8) in which R_1 and R_2 contain only suitable ΔT terms.

VISCOELASTIC STRESS ANALYSIS

Consider Eqs. (9). These equations contain four unknown stresses whose evaluation requires the solution of simultaneous integral equations.

To avoid this cumbersome task we invert the compliances and rewrite (9) to express stresses in terms of ϵ_x , ϵ_y , m and T .

As a first step toward this inversion consider the Laplace transform of (9).

$$\text{Denoting } \bar{F}(p) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-pt} f(t)dt \quad \text{and} \quad p\bar{F}(p) = \tilde{f}(p)$$

we obtain from (9)

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{S}_L \bar{\sigma}_x^0 + \tilde{S}_{12} \bar{\sigma}_y^0 &= \bar{R}_1^0, & \tilde{S}_{12} \bar{\sigma}_x^{90} + \tilde{S}_L \bar{\sigma}_y^{90} &= \bar{R}_2^{90}, \\ \tilde{S}_T \tilde{\sigma}_x^{90} + \tilde{S}_{12} \bar{\sigma}_x^{90} &= \bar{R}_1^{90}, & \tilde{S}_{12} \bar{\sigma}_x^0 + \tilde{S}_T \bar{\sigma}_y^0 &= \bar{R}_2^0 \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Inverting (13) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\sigma}_x^0 &= \tilde{C}_L \bar{R}_1^0 + \tilde{C}_{12} \bar{R}_2^0 & \bar{\sigma}_x^{90} &= \tilde{C}_T \bar{R}_1^{90} + \tilde{C}_{12} \bar{R}_2^{90} \\ \bar{\sigma}_y^0 &= \tilde{C}_{12} \bar{R}_1^0 + \tilde{C}_L \bar{R}_2^0 & \bar{\sigma}_y^{90} &= \tilde{C}_{12} \bar{R}_1^{90} + \tilde{C}_L \bar{R}_2^{90} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

$$\text{where, in (14) } \tilde{C}_L = \frac{\tilde{S}_T}{\Delta}, \quad \tilde{C}_T = \frac{\tilde{S}_L}{\Delta}, \quad \tilde{C}_{12} = -\frac{\tilde{S}_{12}}{\Delta}$$

$$\text{and } \Delta = \tilde{S}_L \tilde{S}_T - \tilde{S}_{12}^2.$$

In the present case, with S_L and S_{12} being constant, the only term which requires attention is S_T .

In view of (5)

$$S_T = D_0 + D_1 t^q$$

consequently

$$\tilde{S}_T = D_0 + D_1 \frac{\Gamma(q+1)}{p^q} \quad (15)$$

We shall employ the approximate form [11], whereby $F(t)$ can be expressed from according to $F(t) \approx \tilde{F}(p) | p = 1/2t$. Therefore (15) yields

$$S_T(t) \approx D_0(1 + At^q) \quad (16)$$

where

$$A = 2^q \frac{D_1 \Gamma(q+1)}{D_0}$$

Similarly, instead of $\tilde{\Delta}$ we shall write, upon inversion

$$\Delta(t) = S_L D_0 (1 + At^q) - S_{12}^2 \quad (17)$$

Altogether, the Laplace transform inversion of (9) will give

$$\sigma_x^0(t) = \int_0^t \left\{ C_L [\xi(t) - \xi(\tau)] \frac{dR_1^0(\tau)}{d\tau} + C_{12} [\xi(t) - \xi(\tau)] \frac{dR_2^0(\tau)}{d\tau} \right\} dt \quad (18)$$

$$\sigma_y^0(t) = \int_0^t \left\{ C_{12} [\xi(t) - \xi(\tau)] \frac{dR_1^0(\tau)}{d\tau} + C_T [\xi(t) - \xi(\tau)] \frac{dR_2^0(\tau)}{d\tau} \right\} dt$$

and similar expressions for $\sigma_x^{90}(t)$ and $\sigma_y^{90}(t)$.

Explicitly in (18), we have $C_L(t) = D_0(1+At^q)/\Delta(t)$, $C_T(t) = S_L/\Delta(t)$,

and $C_{12}(t) = -S_{12}/\Delta(t)$ where $\Delta(t) = S_L D_0(1+At^q) - S_{12}^2$

Just as in the elastic analysis we now have terms $R_1^0(t)$, $R_2^0(t)$, and also $R_1^{90}(t)$ and $R_2^{90}(t)$ which contain known values of moisture $m(z,t)$ and temperature $\Delta T(t)$ and yet unknown strains $\epsilon_x(t)$ and $\epsilon_y(t)$ which are spatially uniform. Those unknown strains are present in order to reassure null resultant forces $\Sigma F_x(t) = 0$, $\Sigma F_y(t) = 0$. Note that the above requirement of null resultants which applies for all times, provides the conditions for the determination of $\epsilon_x(t)$ and $\epsilon_y(t)$ at all times.

In addition, we should note that the viscoelastic analysis considers the initial stresses and strains, $\epsilon_x(0)$ and $\epsilon_y(0)$, and accounts for their own relaxation as time progresses during the conditioning stage.

Finally, in order to clarify matters, we observe that during conditioning the moisture m varies but the temperature T remains constant, therefore $\Delta T = 0$ in R_1^0 , R_2^0 , etc. during that stage.

$$\text{Altogether we have } \sigma_x^0(z,t) = - \left\{ \left[\alpha_L C_L(\xi) + \alpha_T C_{12}(\xi) \right] (T_{\text{cure}} - T_{\text{cond}}) \right. \\ \left. + \left[\beta_L C_L(\xi) + \beta_T C_{12}(\xi) \right] \left[m(z,0) - m_0 \right] \right\} + C_L(\xi) \epsilon_x(0) + C_{12}(\xi) \epsilon_y(0) \\ \left. + \int_0^t \left\{ C_L [\xi(t) - \xi(\tau)] \frac{d\epsilon_x(\tau)}{d\tau} + C_{12} [\xi(t) - \xi(\tau)] \frac{d\epsilon_y(\tau)}{d\tau} \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. - \beta_L C_L [\xi(t) - \xi(\tau)] \frac{dm(z,\tau)}{d\tau} - \beta_T C_{12} [\xi(t) - \xi(\tau)] \frac{d[m(z,\tau) - m_1]}{d\tau} \right\} dt \quad (19)$$

Similar expressions can be derived for $\sigma_x^{90}(z,t)$, $\sigma_y^0(z,t)$ and $\sigma_y^{90}(z,t)$. For details see Ref. [1].

In (19) $m(z,0)$ is the moisture level at the beginning of the conditioning stage. This moisture level, at $t = 0^+$, is taken to be the ambient conditioning moisture level at the outermost surface of the laminate ($z = \pm h$), while the remainder of the laminate remains at the initial moisture level due to storage.

Eq. (19), and its counterparts for σ_x^{90} , σ_y^0 , and σ_y^{90} , express the time-dependent viscoelastic stresses until saturation time $t = t_f$. The value of t_f of course depends on the conditioning temperature T . At $t = t_f$ the temperature is lowered to the room temperature T_R , causing sudden stress increments.

These increments are computed elastically because of their rapid development, which rules out viscoelasticity.

Thus, at time $= t_f^+$ we get

$$\sigma_x^0(z, t_f^+) = \sigma_x^0(z, t_f^-) - [\alpha_L C_L(0) + \alpha_T C_{12}(0)](T_{\text{cond}} - T_R) + C_{12}(0)[\epsilon_y(t_f^+) - \epsilon_y(t_f^-)] + C_L(0)[\epsilon_x(t_f^+) - \epsilon_x(t_f^-)] \quad (20)$$

Analogous expressions can be derived for $\sigma_x^{90}(z, t_f^+)$, $\sigma_y^0(z, t_f^+)$, and $\sigma_y^{90}(z, t_f^+)$. For complete details see Ref. [1].

The time dependent strains $\epsilon_x(t)$ and $\epsilon_y(t)$ are determined from the requirement that $\int_{-h}^h \sigma_x(z, t) dz = 0$ and $\int_{-h}^h \sigma_y(z, t) dz = 0$ at all times t . The thus determined $\epsilon_x(t)$ and $\epsilon_y(t)$ are then reinserted into (19), (20), and the analogous expressions, to yield the actual stress distributions.

In order to perform the computations indicated in (19), we discretize the thickness of the laminate into portions Δz and the time interval into portions Δt . The thickness discretization is required in order to determine the moisture profile at each time and account for its effect on the "reduced time", $\xi = \xi(z, t)$. Furthermore, this discretization is required when performing the integration of stresses across the thickness to obtain $\Sigma F_x = 0$ and $\Sigma F_y = 0$. Satisfactory results were obtained by dividing each ply into five equal increments $\Delta z = 0.00025$ cm.

The discretization of the time domain t into portions Δt between $t_1 = 0$ and the current value t is required to evaluate the time integrals like, say,

$$\int_0^t C_L[\xi(t) - \xi(\tau)] \frac{d\epsilon_x(\tau)}{d\tau} d\tau$$

For this purpose we employ a scheme similar to [12]. Denoting $t_1 = 0$, $t = t_j + 1$ we get

$$\int_0^t C_L[\xi(t) - \xi(\tau)] \frac{d\epsilon_x(\tau)}{d\tau} d\tau = \sum_{k=1}^j \int_{t_k}^{t_{k+1}} C_L[\xi(t) - \xi(\tau)] \frac{d\epsilon_x(\tau)}{d\tau} d\tau \quad (21)$$

$$\approx \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^j \left\{ C_L[\xi(t_{j+1}) - \xi(t_{k+1})] + C_L[\xi(t_{j+1}) - \xi(t_k)] \right\} [\epsilon(t_{k+1}) - \epsilon(t_k)]$$

Expression (21) contains all previously known strains $\epsilon_x(t_1)$, $\epsilon_x(t_2)$,, $\epsilon_x(t_j)$ and the current, yet unknown, strain $\epsilon_x(t_{j+1})$. In this manner the unknown strains $\epsilon_x(t_{j+1})$ and, similarly, $\epsilon_y(t_{j+1})$ are isolated and solved for in a time-marching sequence.

Satisfactory accuracy was obtained by taking six equal increments per decade along the logarithmic time scale.

MATERIAL PROPERTIES AND COMPUTATIONS

The material properties which entered the actual computations are summarized in Table 1 below. Due to the incompleteness of the experimental data it was necessary to employ data for two graphite/epoxy systems. Data marked with a star (*) refers to T300/5208 from Ref. [7], otherwise the data refers to AS/3501-6 from Ref. [9].

The actual computations aim at comparing the stresses for two conditioning environments. In both cases, the initial stresses are identical, and are attributed to the following causes:

Parameter	Symbol	Magnitude
Moisture diffusivity	A_1	$0.016715 \text{ cm}^2/\text{sec}^*$
$D = A_1 \exp(-B_1/T)$ (T in °K)	B_1	4618.0°K^*
Coefficient of moisture expansion per 1% weight gain		
Longitudinal	β_L	$0.^*$
Transverse	β_T	0.4899^*
Moisture offset value	m_1	0.5450^*
Coefficient of thermal expansion		
Longitudinal	α_L	$-0.54 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm/cm/}^\circ\text{K}^*$
Transverse	α_T	$25.74 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm/cm/}^\circ\text{K}^*$
Initial transverse compliance D_0	a	$.12878 \times 10^{-11} \frac{\text{kPa}^{-1}}{^\circ\text{K} \times \text{R.H.}}$
$D_0 = aTH + bT + CH + d$	b	$.14147 \times 10^{-9} \frac{\text{kPa}^{-1}}{^\circ\text{K}}$
	c	$.29075 \times 10^{-9} \frac{\text{kPa}^{-1}}{\text{R.H.}}$
	d	$4.482 \times 10^{-7} \text{ kPa}^{-1}$
Transverse compliance, creep	D_1	$.1631 \times 10^{-8} \text{ kPa}^{-1}/\text{sec.}^q$
Power law exponent	q	0.18
Longitudinal compliance	S_L	$.7653 \times 10^{-8} \text{ kPa}^{-1}$
"Cross effect" compliance	S_{12}	$-.2679 \times 10^{-8} \text{ kPa}^{-1}$
Temperature shift factor function	a_3	-105.5
Eq. (6) ₁	a_4	$6.183 \times 10^4 \text{ }^\circ\text{K}$
	a_5	$-9.053 \times 10^6 \text{ }^\circ\text{K}^2$
Moisture shift factor function	a_6	$.06336$
$a_2 = a_6 \times (\%m)^{b_1}$	b_1	-8.942
Moisture to R.H. conversion factor	E	$.01505^*$
$m = E \times (\%R.H.)$		

Table 1. Material Properties

1. Cool-down from a cure temperature, $T_{\text{cure}} = 450^\circ\text{K}$ (350°F) to room temperature, $T_{\text{room}} = 297^\circ\text{K}$ (75°F).
2. Uniform moisture saturation during storage due to 50% relative humidity.

In actuality, the effect of the temperature rise from $T_{\text{room}} = 75^\circ\text{F}$ to the conditioning temperature is incorporated into the initial conditions.

The two conditioning environments are:

1. 339°K (150°F) at 98% R.H.
2. 355°K (180°F) at 98% R.H.

The magnitudes of material parameters, which are dependent on the conditioning environment, are calculated for each environment and summarized in Table 2.

Results are shown for $[0_2/90_2]_s$ laminates. Further results, for other lay-ups are given in [1].

Parameter	Symbol	Conditioning Temperature		Units
		339°K	355°K	
Moisture diffusivity	D	$.2000 \times 10^{-8}$	$.3798 \times 10^{-8}$	$\text{cm}^2/\text{sec.}$
Initial transverse	D_0	$.1063 \times 10^{-6}$	$.1102 \times 10^{-6}$	kPa^{-1}
Temperature shift factor function	a_1	0.0137	0.00063	
Elastic moduli	C_L	131.1×10^6	131.8×10^6	kPa
	C_T	9.45×10^6	9.17×10^6	kPa
	C_{12}	3.303×10^6	3.203×10^6	kPa

Table 2. Conditioning Dependent Material Properties

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figs. 3 and 4 exhibit the stresses $\sigma_x(z,t)$ and $\sigma_y(z,t)$ due to moisture sorption at 98% R.H. These figures provide comparisons between conditioning at 339°K (dashed lines) and at 355°K (solid lines) and demonstrate the "competition" between the effects of moisture and temperature as stress inducing agents on one hand and stress-relaxing parameters on the other hand.

Fig. 3. The Viscoelastic Stresses σ_x Vs. The Spatial Coordinate z at Various Times t for $[O_2/90O_2]_s$ laminate ($z = 0$ is Symmetry Plane) Due to Moisture Conditioning at 98% R.H. at 355°K (Solid Lines) and 339°K (Dashed Lines). σ in mPa (ksi in parentheses).

Fig. 4. The Viscoelastic Stresses σ_y Vs. The Spatial Coordinate z at Various Times t for $[0_2/90_2]_S$ Laminate ($z = 0$ is Symmetry Plane) Due to Moisture Conditioning at 98% R.H. at 355°K (Solid Lines) and 339°K (Dashed Lines). σ in mPa (ksi in Parentheses).

To appreciate the total effect of conditioning, consider the stresses σ_y at each conditioning temperature (Fig. 4). During the early stages of conditioning, $t = 1$ minute, for which there has been but minimal added moisture, the stress profiles reflect the difference between the two conditioning temperatures. However, as conditioning progresses, say up to 1000 minutes, the dependence of moisture sorption and the stress relaxation on the conditioning temperature becomes prominent. At this stage, there is noticeably more moisture sorption at 355°K than at 339°K as is evident by the larger compressive stresses in the transverse direction of the outer ply. Yet, at the outer surface of the laminate, where the boundaries were exposed to the ambient conditioning moisture level throughout the entire 1000 minutes of the conditioning stage, the compressive stresses are about 17 percent lower for the conditioning environment of 355°K. After 10,000 minutes we note that the slopes of the transverse stresses in the outer ply are of opposite signs. This contrast is attributed to the enhanced relaxation at 355°K. Finally, upon reaching moisture saturation (≈ 22 days at 355°K, and 43 days at 339°K), the stress profile in both the longitudinal and transverse directions is nearly uniform across the thickness; yet, the fact that the stress magnitudes are similar is purely

Fig. 5. The Stresses σ_y Vs. The Spatial Coordinate z at Various Times t Due to Conditioning at 98% R.H. at 355°K. Viscoelastic Results (Solid Lines) Vs. Linear Elastic Predictions (Dashed Lines). σ in mPa (ksi in parentheses).

coincidental.

The final cool-down to room temperature of 297°K superimposes additional stresses on the laminate. However, since conditioning at a lower temperature corresponds to a smaller stress increment, the stresses due to conditioning at 339°K are lower than those stresses resulting from conditioning at 355°K. Note also that the locations of tensile and compressive stresses are reversed.

For comparative purposes, the elastic and viscoelastic stresses are presented in Fig. 5 for conditioning at 355°K.

The figure shows that by discarding time-dependent response and overlooking stress relaxation the elastic analysis predicts stresses which differ from the viscoelastic results in sign and overestimates them by three to six fold.

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